

EXPERIMENTAL AND SIMULATION STUDY ON TRISTABLE BEHAVIOUR OF CROSS-SHAPED UNSYMMETRIC FIBER-REINFORCED CROSS-PLY LAMINATES

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This paper presents a cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates, which is different from square-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates and has three stable configurations. The third stable equilibrium configurations is a transition stable state which is occur in the snap process from first to second equilibrium configurations. The snap process, including first-third-second and second-third-first, between different stable equilibrium configurations of a tristable cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates is investigated by experiment and simulation methods. The parameters used to characterize the tristable performances of the laminates, including stress distributions of the laminates in the second and third stable states, principle curvature, snap load and displacement are measured. Load-displacement curves and buckling phenomena in the snapping process are successfully captured. The influences of material properties, geometrical parameters and the thickness of single layer on the tristable performance of cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates are discussed. The results show that experimental and simulation results agree very well.

1 INTRODUCTION

Multistable composite structures are characterized by having at least two stable configurations, where each configuration represents a different geometric shape and has the ability to sustain significant changes in shape without a continuous power supply, which makes them suitable for applications in deployable and morphing structures[1-4]. In addition, the shape that is obtained after cure process can be snapped into another stable shape under the action of a force or moment. Recently, other interesting applications have been proposed, such as aerospace [5-10], bionic structures[11-14], isolators[15, 16], gearless motor [17], energy harvesting systems[18-28], or anti-icing system [29]. Multistable structures may be the most attractive for engineering design purposes in view of the various alternative geometric configurations they provide.

A multistable structure can be obtained in several ways, for example through thermal effects in unsymmetric composite structures [30-33], pre-stress or plastic deformations [34, 35], or an appropriate choice of geometry shape and material properties [36-38], the variable stiffness composites that allow the fiber orientation to vary continuously throughout the laminate [39]. However, most of the multistable structures reported in the open literature are dominated by the bistable unsymmetric composite laminates. In order to capture room-temperature shapes, Hyer developed the classical laminate theory based on the von-Karman geometric nonlinearities and the Rayleigh-Ritz method according to the concept of the minimum potential energy [30, 40, 41]. Hamamoto and Hyer [42] studied the relationship between the temperature and the curvature of unsymmetric graphite-epoxy laminates cured at an elevated temperature according to a geometrically nonlinear theory and indicated that above a certain temperature range, the temperature-curvature relationship of unsymmetric laminates can bifurcate and be triple-valued. There is another kind of

bistable structure, which has an anti-symmetric stacking sequence [29, 33, 43-49]. The curvatures of the two stable equilibria of the anti-symmetric laminate have the same direction.

To induce the snap-through process from one stable state to another, the actuator such as piezoelectric actuation, shape memory alloy (SMA) actuation, thermal actuation, and magnetic actuation have been employed. Schultz et al. [50] have taken the advantage of smart materials and have investigated the morphing and deployable structures. A bistable cantilever with piezoelectric actuators was presented by Bowen et al. [51]. Hufenbach et al. [52] designed a smart prototype of a multistable composite integrated with SMA based on theoretical investigations. investigated unsymmetric bistable laminates actuated by SMA wires to achieve a reversible state change. Giddings et al. [53] characterized the components and construction of bistable laminates and their structural response under a range of temperature conditions. Eckstein et al. [54] studied the snap-through of fibre-metal hybrid laminates driven by temperature changes. Zhang et al. [12] designed a non-contact magnetic driving bioinspired Venus flytrap robot, where the magnetic actuator was located on the curved edge of the bistable laminates. The structure deformed slowly in the triggering process but closed rapidly in the snap-through process.

To investigate the characteristics and applications of multistable composite laminates, actuation experiments were performed. Hyer et al. [55] presented a force-controlled experiment to measure the snap-through process and the characteristics of the configuration. The predicted moment-strain relationship is in good agreement with the experimental measurements. To describe the snap-through process, a test rig consisting of two flat plates held at a fixed-distance was designed by Kevin to measure the load-deflection curves [56]. Zhang et al. [49] proposed the “two-point loading” method to investigate the bistable transition of antisymmetric laminate cylindrical shells. Lei et al. [57, 58] used a charge-coupled device to record the morphing process of a thin shell.

The finite element method (FEM) has also been used to study bistable behaviour of cured unsymmetric laminates and allows general laminates to be modelled with fairly good accuracy [59, 60]. Cho et al. [61] presented a FE model of unsymmetric laminates with layups of $[0_2/90_2]$, $[0/90_3]$, etc. The measured results were closer to the finite element results than the theoretical results. Giddings et al. [53] investigated the influence of manufacturing imperfections, such as resin-rich areas and ply-thickness variations, and used two types of FE models—an “idealised model” and an “improved model”—to predict the stable shapes of cured bistable laminates. Using the FEM and a new analytical formulation, Mattioni et al. [62, 63] suggested that it is possible to introduce bistable composites within structures to obtain systems that are both flexible and stiff depending on the load environment. Moore et al. [64] considered the stability characteristics and the thermal response of laminates with different unsymmetric compositions using the nonlinear FEM. Dai et al. [32, 65] used ABAQUS to construct a model with a layup of $[90_n/Al/90_n]TU[90_n/0_m/90_n]TU[90_n/Al/90_n]T$. A disturbance was applied to the finite element model during the cooling process to obtain the stable configurations, and the curing process was captured by simulations, which were in good agreement with the analytical prediction.

In this paper, a cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates with tristable equilibrium configurations is proposed. The third stable equilibrium configurations is a stable transition state which occurs in the snap process from first to second equilibrium configurations. The experiment and simulation methods are used to investigate the snap-through and snap-back process, between different stable equilibrium configurations of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates. To characterize the tristable performances of the laminates, the stress distributions of the laminates in the second and third stable states, and snap load and displacement are measured by experiment and simulation. Load-displacement curves and buckling phenomena during the snap process are successfully captured. The effects of material properties, geometrical sizes and the thickness of single layer on the tristable performance of cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates are discussed. The results show that the experimental results agree well with the simulation results.

2 EXPERIMENT SETUP

The experiments were set up to study the snap-through and snap-back behaviors and shape characteristics of the cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates. The cross-shaped

carbon fiber prepregs of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates were cut from square carbon fiber prepregs. The cross-shaped laminates are fabricated on a flat plate with a cross shape, cured at a high temperature, and allowed to cool to room temperature.

Fig. 1 shows the geometry of a cross-shaped laminate. The cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate is symmetrical about the x - and y -directions. Therefore, the geometry of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate can be characterized by the side lengths Lx_1 , Lx_2 , Ly_1 , and Ly_2 , which are the planform dimensions along the x - and y -directions. In this paper, the side lengths of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates— Lx_1 , Lx_2 , Ly_1 , and Ly_2 —are assumed to be equal, so that $Ls=Lx_1=Lx_2=Ly_1=Ly_2$. To investigate the shapes and the snap-through and snap-back behaviors of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate with respect to the material properties, the thickness of single layer and the side length, the selected carbon fiber prepregs are T300 and T700, the thickness of single layers are 0.1mm, 0.15mm and 0.2mm and the side length of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate are 30mm, 40mm, 50mm with a stacking sequence of [0/90]. The three stable configurations A, C and B of a cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Geometry of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates.

(1) configuration A (2) configuration C (3) configuration B

Fig. 2: Three stable configurations A, C and B of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate

To describe the geometry shape of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates, which have been divided into five parts by red dotted line shown in Fig. 1. The principle curvature of each part will be captured by the three dimensional scanner. Due to the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates is symmetrical about the x - and y -directions, the geometry shape of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate can be characterized by the curvatures R_1 , R_2 , and R_3 , where the subscripts represent different parts. As shown in Fig. 2, the stable configuration B is irregular shape, so that R_{3x} , R_{3y} curvature along the x - and y -directions are used to character the shape of part 3. The geometry shape of each part for specimens were measured by three dimensional scanner as shown in Fig. 3, the specimen was placed on the plate and three dimensional scanner scanned the specimens from different angles and displayed on the monitor. Then, the geometric shape and the curvature of each part of the specimen can be obtained by Geomagic software.

Fig. 3: The assembly of the three dimensional scanner.

To study the snap-through process of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates, the specimens were measured by a universal tensile testing machine as shown in Fig. 4, the specimen was placed on the support and the indenter moved downward, the reaction force on the indenter can be captured by the high precision mechanical sensor and displayed on the monitor. Related parameters of the universal tensile testing machine are listed as follow: 1) the mechanical sensor was selected with a measurement range of 0-50N; 2) the measuring error of the testing machine was less than 0.5%. Interruption conditions should be established to guarantee the safety of the equipment. Thus, loading would be interrupted under the following conditions: in order to prevent the experiment from stopping due to the snap process, the interruption condition is that the displacement reaches 20mm. Moreover, the loading speed in this experiment is 5mm/min.

Fig. 4: The assembly of universal tensile testing machine.

For the loading scheme of configurations A and Band C, a concentrated force was applied to the central point of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate, and the two supports are placed symmetrically. The critical loads to induce the snap-through process and the displacement of the indenter were measured in the experiments. The relationship between the load and the displacement of the indenter was also investigated to characterize the tristable behaviour of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates. Shown in Fig. 5 are the whole snapping processes of the cross-shaped laminate observed in experiments, including first-third-second and second-third-first processes.

Fig. 5: The snapping process, including (a) snap-through process: A-C-B and (b) snap-back process: B-C-A, between different stable equilibrium configurations.

3. NUMERICAL SIMULATION

In this section, the commercial finite element software ABAQUS is used to simulate the curing process, the snap-through process and the snap-back process of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates. The material properties of the T300 and T700 reinforced composite laminates used in the simulation are listed in Table 1.

properties	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	α_1 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	α_2 ($^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$)	ν_{12}
T300	138	8.36	4.51	-1.06E-007	2.56E-005	0.27
T700	110	7.07	4.00	-9E-007	2.528E-005	0.31

Table 1. Mechanical properties of the T300 and T700 reinforced composite laminates.

A restart method is proposed. First, the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates are modeled by shell planar of 3D deformable shell. The stacking sequence of the composite laminate is [0/90], and the thickness of a single layer t is same with that in experiments. In the first model, the geometric centre of the laminate is clamped to suppress the rigid body motion and to reproduce free-free boundary conditions. An initial temperature field reflecting the elevated curing temperature is applied. The cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates are meshed by the S4R shell element to provide more accurate results and significantly reduce the computational time, as shown in Fig 6. The simulation is aimed at the curing process, and the analysis process is divided into two steps: Step-1 is a heating process, in

which an integral temperature field is applied to the laminate; Step-2 is a cooling process and ‘Restart Requests’ are needed in the output option. In each step, the nonlinear large deformation option ‘Nlgeom’ is ‘on’, and ‘Automatic Stabilization’ is set according to the default parameters to make the simulation results convergemore easily.

Fig. 6. Finite element model and stacking arrangement of the unsymmetric cross-shaped laminate in ABAQUS.

For the snap-through process, the model of cross-shaped laminates is imported from the ODB file of the curing process. The supports and indenter are modelled by discrete rigids. The supports are rigid and smooth, with their 'Displacement/Rotation' boundary conditions constrained to support the shell. The node-to-surface contacts are established to simulate the interactions between the specimens and the support and between the specimens and the indenter. A reference point is created at one end of the indenter. The analysis process is divided into four steps: Step-1 is the loading process, a load is applied through moving the indenter downward in the z -direction. As the indenter moves along the z -direction, the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates snaps from stable state A to C; Step-2 is the unloading process, the indenter returns to the origin of coordinates along the z -direction to obtain the stable state C; Step-3 is also load process, the load is applied through changing the displacement of the indenter in the z -direction but the displacement is more larger than Step-1. As a result, the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates snaps from C stable state to the B stable state; Step-4 is a unload process and a restart requests are needed in the output option. The indenter moves back to the origin of coordinates along the z -direction to ensure the B stable state of cross-shaped laminates is occur. The FEM results of the three stable configurations A, B and C of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates were illustrated in Fig. 7. The static/general solver and the automatic stabilization are used to carry out a pseudo-dynamic nonlinear simulation to capture the snap behaviour. Similar to the experimental case, Fig. 8 presents the assembly of each part.

(1) Configuration A (2) Configuration C (3) Configuration B

Fig. 7. The cross-shaped laminate with three stable configurations A, C and B using the FEM.

Fig. 8. The assembly of each part.

The laminates with the stable shape B was placed on the smooth supports using the option restart requests in snap-through process and loaded by the downward movement of the indenter so that a snap-back process can be induced in FEM as shown in Fig. 9, where von Mises stress is represented by the contour. The simulation of snap-back process is similar to that of the snap-through process. The shell snaps from the stable state B to A with the indenter moving downward.

Fig. 9. The snap process of unsymmetric cross-shaped composite laminates in ABAQUS software

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1. Comparison between the experimental and numerical results

As discussed above, the second and third stable shapes are important for studying the tristable behavior of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates. The parameters of the specimen are as follows: carbon fibre is T700, $L_s = 50\text{mm}$, $t = 0.15\text{mm}$, layup is $[0/90]$. Fig. 10 shows three stable shapes of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates and their von Mises stress contour plot. It can be seen that the von Mises stress is symmetric about the x and y axes, and the maximum von Mises stress with a magnitude of 51.15MPa is located at the vertex of configuration A, 85.90MPa is on the angle of the cross of configuration C, 77.91MPa is on the side of the high part of configuration B.

(a) Configuration A

(b) Configuration C

(c) Configuration B

Fig. 10. Three stable shapes of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates from the numerical simulation

The load-displacement curves of snap-through process for specimen that are used to describe a laminates deformation process from stable shape A to stable shape C and to stable shape B are shown in Fig. 11, where the red lines and black lines represent numerical and experimental results respectively. The laminate with a larger transverse radius has a smaller snap load and transforms into the other stable shape under a smaller displacement loading. The overall trends of the load-displacement curves from experiment and simulation are similar. The load increases steadily with displacement until interrupted by a sudden downward change where one side of the part of cross-shaped laminates in contact with the supports will transform first, followed by a steep increase until interrupted again by a sudden downward change where the other side of the laminate changes and the structure reaches stable shape C. At this time, the snap process from state A to C is completed, and the position of the indenter is lower than the position of center point of the stable shape C in the z-axis direction, so the force is nonzero. When the snap process from state C to B occurs, the load increases steadily with displacement until interrupted by a sudden downward change, which is similar to that of state A to C snap process. The load-displacement curve of the numerical results is just directly sudden downward to zero, because the specimen is completely symmetrical in the simulation but not completely symmetrical in the experiment. But the snap load is less than that of the snap process from

A to C, which means the snap process from stable state C to B is easier to occur compared with the snap process from stable state A to C.

Fig. 11. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-through process

The snap-back process is used to describe the deformation process from the stable shape B to C and then to A, as the reverse process of snap-through process, it is an important component for the tristability study of cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply laminates. Fig. 12 shows the load-displacement curves of the snap-back process predicted by the numerical simulation and experiment. As can be seen, simulation and experiment results agree well. The load has an approximately linear relationship with the displacement before reaching its peak value, and then an abrupt decrease happens, where the structure reaches stable shape C. Meanwhile, the position of the indenter is higher than the position of center point of stable shape C along the z -axis direction, so the force is zero. As the displacement increases, the indenter contacts the specimen again, and then the load increases steadily with displacement until interrupted by a sudden downward change where one side of the part of cross-shaped laminates in non-contact with supports transforms first, followed by a steep increase with displacement until interrupted by a sudden downward change where the other side change and the structure reaches its initial state A. The load from simulation decreases suddenly to zero because the laminates is completely symmetrical. The snap load is larger than that of the snap process from C to A, which means the snap process from C to A is easier to occur compared with the snap process from B to C.

Fig. 12. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-back process

The displacement (D), snap load (F) of snap process for different stable states are listed in Table 2. D_{te} and D_{tf} represent the displacements of the snap-through, D_{be} and D_{bf} are the displacements of the snap-back, F_{te} and F_{tf} indicate the snap loads of the snap-through, F_{be} and F_{bf} are the snap loads of the snap-back, where the subscript e and f represent the results from the experiment and numerical simulation, respectively.

It is seen that the snap load of C-B process is approximately half of A-C process, and the snap load of C-B process is higher than that of C-A process, which means the laminate is more likely to transform into stable shape A when it is in stable shape C. The displacements D for snap-through process A-B is less than the sum of displacements for snap-through A-C and C-B process, because the position of the indenter is lower than the position of center of stable shape C when the laminate completes the snap process from A to C. However, the opposite phenomenon occurs in snap-back process, the displacements for B-A process is high than the sum of displacements of B-C and C-A process because the indenter and the specimen are separate when the snap process from B to C is completed. The results of displacement (D), snap load (F) from both the experiment and the simulation are in good agreement.

Fig. 13 shows that the geometry shape of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates is capture by experiment and simulation. The simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental results. In the A and C configuration state, the principal curvatures are opposite, while in the B configuration state, the results of simulation and experiment are all irregular geometric shapes in part 3, and the principal curvatures of the parts 1 and 4 bend along different coordinate axes in opposite directions to the parts 2 and 5. The principal curvature of different configurations from both the experiment and the simulation are shown in Table 3. It is seen that the principal curvature of configuration A and B are approximately the same in size and opposite in direction, and the value of the principle curvature of parts 1, 2 and 3 are similar. While the value of principle curvature for parts 1 and 2 of configuration C are also approximately similar, but the principle curvature for part 3 of configuration C is much less than that of parts 1 and 2. And the R_{3x} is greater than R_{3y} . Moreover, the results of principle curvature from the simulation are less than that from the experiment. The possible reasons are as follow: errors in specimen manufacturing; scanning errors in 3D scanner when scanning specimens; errors in Geomagic software when repairing scanning results.

Snap process	Snap-load (F)				Displacement (D)			
	F_{te} (N)	F_{tf} (N)	F_{be} (N)	F_{bf} (N)	D_{te} (mm)	D_{tf} (mm)	D_{be} (mm)	D_{bf} (mm)
A-C	2.60	2.63	0.83	0.85	4.04	4.36	2.44	2.37
B-C	2.16	2.34	1.43	1.39	2.31	2.47	5.33	4.17
A-B	2.60	2.63	2.16	2.34	8.01	7.02	7.21	6.47

Table 2. The displacement and snap load of snap process from both the experiment and the simulation

configurations	R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3xe}	R_{3ye}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3xf}	R_{3yf}
A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680	/
C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044	1.0905
B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/	8.4812

Table 3. The principal curvature of different configurations from both the experiment and the simulation

(a) Configuration A

(b) Configuration C

(c) Configuration B

Fig. 13. The geometric shapes of the cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates from the experiment and numerical simulation

4.2 Factors affecting the bistable behaviors

In order to study the factors affecting the tristable behavior and snap process of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates, specimens with various geometric sizes and material properties are manufactured and divided into three groups. In each group, only one factor is allowed to change and other geometric parameters remain unchanged. More specimens are modelled through FEM for a comparison with the experimental results, by which the influences of geometric parameters and material properties on the tristable performances can be examined. Displacement D , snap load F , load-displacement curves and principle curvature are reported for characterization of tristable behavior of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates.

4.2.1 Reinforced material

The experimental load-displacement curves of snap-through process from configuration A to B for the cross-shaped laminates reinforced with T300 and T700 carbon fibers are shown in Fig. 14. It is obvious from Fig. 14 that the displacement and snap load of T300 carbon fiber reinforced laminates is larger than that of T700. The same phenomenon also appears in the snap-back process of the cross-shaped laminates, as shown in Fig. 15. But the trend of load-displacement curve of snap-back process of T300 is similar to that of snap-through process, but is different with that of snap-back process from B to C. Table 4 shows the displacement and snap load from both the experiment and the simulation, where the snap loads agree well. The displacement results from simulation are less than that from experiment since the specimens manufactured by carbon fiber prepregs are not symmetrical. Table 5 presents the principal curvature of configuration states with different reinforced materials from both the experiment and the simulation, where the principal curvature of T700 carbon fiber reinforced laminates is less than that of T300 carbon fiber reinforced laminates and the results are in good

agreement. These results show that carbon fiber properties have a significant effect on the principal curvature, snap load and displacement of the laminates.

Fig. 14. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-through process with different reinforced materials in the experiment.

Fig. 15. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-back process with different reinforced materials in the experiment.

A-B reinforced materials	Snap-load (F)				Displacement (D)			
	F_{1e} (N)	F_{1f} (N)	F_{2e} (N)	F_{2f} (N)	D_{1e} (mm)	D_{1f} (mm)	D_{2e} (mm)	D_{2f} (mm)
T300	4.57	4.63	2.72	2.87	11.78	9.98	9.04	7.51
T700	2.60	2.63	2.16	2.34	8.01	7.02	7.21	6.47

Table 4. The displacement and snap load of A-B process with different reinforced materials from both the experiment and the simulation

Specimens	R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3xe}	R_{3ye}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3xf}	R_{3yf}
T700 A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680	/

	C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044	1.0905
	B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/	8.4812
	A	11.3296	11.4238	11.4812	/	12.1140	12.2324	12.2896	/
T300	C	11.4947	11.5053	2.6349	0.3328	12.3342	12.4103	2.5864	0.5324
	B	11.5376	11.5145	/	11.4792	12.3863	12.2408	/	12.2585

Table 5. The principal curvature of configuration states with different reinforced materials from both the experiment and the simulation

4.2.2 The thickness of single layer

Fig. 16. shows the load-displacement curves of the snap-through process from configuration A to B for cross-shaped laminates with different thicknesses t of single layer. As it is evident from Fig. 16, laminates with different t have similar response in the snapping behavior. However, a smaller thickness leads to a smaller snap load and a significantly larger displacement. More displacements are needed to complete the snap-through process because the laminates curl more obviously at A or B stable shape when the thickness is 0.1mm. Fig. 17 shows the snap-back process curves for $t=0.1\text{mm}$, 0.15mm and 0.2mm. With the increase of thickness, the load increases and the displacement decreases. The load-displacement curves of the laminates with layer thickness of 0.2mm are obviously different from those of $t=0.1\text{mm}$ and 0.15mm. The displacement of the B-A process is less than the sum of the displacements of the B-C process and C-A process, because the stiffness of the laminates increases with the increase of the thickness. During the snap process, the laminates will snap directly to stable shape C. The displacement (D) and snap load (F) results for different thickness t are listed in Table 6, where the experimental results conform well to the simulation ones. Table 7 shows the principal curvature of configuration states with different thickness of single layer of the cross-shaped laminates from both the experiment and the simulation, where the results agree well. With the increase of thickness of single layer, principle curvature increases and the increase of principal curvature decreases. All these indicate that the thickness of single layer t obviously has significant influence on the tristable behaviour and geometry of laminates.

Fig. 16. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-through process with different thickness of single layer in the experiment.

Fig. 17. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-back process with different thickness of single layer in the experiment.

A-B	Snap-load (F)				Displacement (D)			
	F_{te} (N)	F_{tf} (N)	F_{be} (N)	F_{bf} (N)	D_{te} (mm)	D_{tf} (mm)	D_{be} (mm)	D_{bf} (mm)
0.10mm	2.19	2.21	1.70	2.01	15.48	12.11	13.53	13.16
0.15mm	2.60	2.63	2.16	2.34	8.01	7.02	7.21	6.47
0.20mm	6.07	6.41	3.99	4.18	7.58	7.13	3.03	3.14

Table 6. The displacement and snap load of A-B process with different thickness of single layer of the cross-shaped laminates from both the experiment and the simulation

Specimens	R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3xe}	R_{3ye}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3xf}	R_{3yf}
0.10mm	A	14.2326	14.2271	14.5764	/	15.0243	15.0772	15.3993
	C	14.1936	14.2763	2.4206	1.3965	14.9058	15.0750	2.6198
	B	14.3144	14.3212	/	14.3953	15.2711	15.1474	/
0.15mm	A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680
	C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044
	B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/
0.20mm	A	7.4217	7.4603	7.4522	/	7.3839	7.5038	7.5552
	C	7.9856	7.6964	1.4739	0.8846	7.9217	7.7484	1.4929
	B	7.8206	7.5109	/	7.5044	7.6097	7.4889	/

Table 7. The principal curvature of configuration states with different thickness of single layer of the cross-shaped laminates from both the experiment and the simulation

4.2.3 Sidlength

The load-displacement curves of the snap-through processes for the cross-shaped laminates with different sidelengths L_s are plotted in Fig. 18, showing that a larger sidelength leads to a greater snap load and a larger displacement. As the sidelength decreases, laminates will no longer have multistability, for example the sidelength is 20mm. For a sidelength of 30mm, stable shape A of

laminates is more stable than stable state B, C and only needs a very small force to snap. Fig. 19 shows that the snap load and displacement of the snap-back process increase with the increase of the sidelength, but when the sidelength is 30mm, the snap load of the B-C process is less than that of the C-A process, which means that it is easier for the laminates to change from stable shape B to C. The displacement and snap load results for the laminates with different sidelengths from the experiment and simulation are listed in Table 8, where the experiment and simulation results are in good agreement. Table 9 shows the principal curvature of configuration states with different sidelength L_s from both the experiment and the simulation, where the results are in a good agreement. The principal curvature and sidelength L_s present a positive linear correlation, and as the sidelength L_s is reduced to 30mm, the laminate will not appear configuration B state. In conclusion, sidelength L_s has an important effect on snapping processes and geometry of the laminates.

All the comparison studies show that the experimental results agree well with the numerical predictions although some reasonable discrepancies exist. It can be found that the type of carbon fiber and thickness are the most important factors that influence the snap load and displacement of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates. However, the side length determines whether the laminate has multistability or not.

Fig. 18. Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-through process with different sidelengths L_s in the experiment.

Fig. 19: Comparison of load-displacement curves of snap-back process with different sidelengths L_s in the experiment.

A-B	Snap-load (F)				Displacement (D)				
	L_s	F_{te} (N)	F_{tf} (N)	F_{be} (N)	F_{bf} (N)	D_{te} (mm)	D_{tf} (mm)	D_{be} (mm)	D_{bf} (mm)
50mm		2.60	2.63	2.16	2.34	8.01	7.02	7.21	6.47
40mm		1.18	1.33	0.74	0.76	7.63	7.28	2.55	2.74
30mm		0.54	0.55	0.24	0.29	5.76	5.30	2.06	2.33

Table 8: The displacement and snap load of A-B process with different sidelength L_s from both the experiment and the simulation

Specimens	R_{1e}	R_{2e}	R_{3xe}	R_{3ye}	R_{1f}	R_{2f}	R_{3xf}	R_{3yf}	
50mm	A	7.9968	8.2968	8.1065	/	8.3826	8.5438	8.4680	/
	C	8.2418	8.1947	1.6079	1.1811	8.7387	8.6052	1.7044	1.0905
	B	8.1537	7.9867	/	8.0176	8.5742	8.4031	/	8.4812
40mm	A	7.7362	8.0394	8.0102	/	7.9306	8.4354	8.1968	/
	C	8.1166	7.9250	2.2390	1.5937	8.3124	8.1325	2.4007	1.6694
	B	7.9051	7.8693	/	8.1902	8.1138	7.8324	/	8.2005
30mm	A	7.5402	7.2930	8.1629	/	7.7187	7.3299	8.3596	/
	C	/	/	/	/	8.0465	8.3530	4.4276	2.0602
	B	7.4925	7.2601	/	8.1403	7.4738	7.2785	/	8.3334

Table 9: The principal curvature of configuration states with different sidelength L_s from both the experiment and the simulation

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a cross-shaped unsymmetric fiber-reinforced cross-ply with tristable equilibrium configurations. The snap process between different stable equilibrium configurations of a cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates investigated by experiment and simulation methods. The von Mises stress of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates is symmetric about the x and y axes, and the maximum von Mises stress is located at different place of different configurations. Load-displacement curves and buckling phenomena in the snap process are successfully captured. The cross-shaped unsymmetric laminate is more likely to transform into stable shape A when it is in stable shape C. The displacements D for snap-through process A-B is less than the sum of displacements for snap-through A-C and C-B process, while the opposite phenomenon occurs in snap-back process. Experiment and simulation results show that the type of carbon fiber and thickness are the most important factors that influence the principle curvature snap load and displacement of cross-shaped unsymmetric laminates. However, the side length determines whether the laminate has multistability or not.

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